

Distribution update for *Compsogusa rhea* Schwarz, 2021

Kris Anderson

A female specimen of *Compsogusa rhea* Schwarz, 2021, previously understood to be precinctive to Panay Island, has been discovered from the Calabarzon region of Luzon Island in the Quezon province of the Philippines. The pinned specimen lost its natural pigmentation of mottled green and brown and faded to a light tan through desiccation. Photographs of the voucher specimen after it was freshly harvested are provided to demonstrate its natural coloration. Additional photographs of pinned specimens demonstrate the comparison of the sympatric *C. luzoni* Anderson, 2022.

A, dorsal habitus; B, ventral habitus. *Compsogusa rhea* ♀ of Luzon Island, Philippines.

C, interior surface of prothoracic leg. *Compsogusa rhea* ♀ of Luzon Island, Philippines.

D, dorsal habitus of dried, pinned specimens. *Compsogusa rhea* ♀ of Luzon Island (left) vs *Compsogusa luzoni* ♀ of Luzon Island (right).

E & F, dorsal habitus of freshly harvested specimens. *Compsogusa rheae* ♀ of Luzon Island (top) vs *Compsogusa luzoni* ♀ of Luzon Island (bottom).

In addition to the overall loss of greenish pigmentation throughout the body and forewings, the darker foreleg and pronotal maculations that are present in living specimens significantly fade during the drying process. The measurements of the *rheae* voucher specimen from Luzon are as follows:

Measurements. (All measurements are in millimeters and rounded to nearest 0.5) Body length 28; pronotum length 6.5; forewing length 14; prothoracic coxa length 5; prothoracic femur length 7.5; metathoracic femur length 8.

Figure Plate 1. Distribution range map of *Compsogusa*

	<i>C. luzoni</i>	<i>C. rheae</i>	<i>C. aff. rheae</i>
PHILIPPINES			
Balabac			
Basilan			
Biliran			
Bohol			
Burias			
Busuanga			
Calayan			
Camiguin			
Catanduanes			
Cebu			
Culion			
Dinagat			
Dumaran			
Guimaras			
Jolo			
Leyte			
Luzon	X	X	
Marinduque			
Masbate			
Mindanao			X
Mindoro			
Negros			
Palawan			
Panay		X	
Polillo			
Samal			
Samar			
Siargao			
Sibutu			
Sibuyan			
Siquijor			
Tablas			
Tawitawi			
Ticao			

Figure Plate 2. Occurrence of different *Compsogusa* species in the main islands of the Philippines

Material Examined.

Pinned Specimen of *Compsogusa rhea*: 1 ♀ Real, Quezon Province, Calabarzon Region, Luzon Island, Philippines 10.2021, BLumawig leg. Anderson Collection Las Vegas.

Female Holotype of *Compsogusa luzoni*: Lagonoy, Camarines Sur Province, Bicol Region, Luzon Island, Philippines 11.2018, BLumawig leg. Anderson Collection Las Vegas.

References.

ANDERSON, K. (2022): New Species of *Compsogusa* Schwarz, 2021 from the Philippines. Soothsayer, Journal of Mantodea Research. 3 (1): 104-118.

SCHWARZ, C. (2021): Three New Praying Mantises from Panay Island, Philippines. – Integrative Systematics: Stuttgart Contributions to Natural History, 2 (1): 35-56.

To cite this article: Anderson, K. (2023): Distribution update for *Compsogusa rhea* Schwarz, 2021. Soothsayer, Journal of Mantodea Research. 4 (1): 3-8.